

“Psychological aspects of a person's self-awareness”

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Abstract: *In this article, the self-awareness of the individual, the psychological aspects of the self, the research conducted by foreign psychologists on the self-awareness of the individual, I.S. Introduction of the concept of "I" to science, the concept of "I", the study of individual self-management in world psychology, psychological aspects of self-management, and the structure of self-regulation. Information is stated.*

Key words: *Self-awareness, self-management, adolescent personality, cognitive and affective component, self-regulation, leadership activity.*

People have been interested in questions about themselves since the dawn of mankind. Various debates and questions arose about who a person really is, how he was born, how he lived and how he should live, and other topics.

According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, self-awareness is defined as "awareness of actions or situations that belong to oneself and arise from oneself." Psychological characteristics of self-awareness in the science of social psychology, self-awareness, moral self-awareness as a socio-spiritual phenomenon, a process from a separate scientific point of view not studied. it is analyzed in direct connection with the categories of ethics, national character, national spirituality and values. Elucidating these categories in a unique way creates an opportunity to clearly

understand the person, his place in the group (community), the importance of interpersonal relations, which is the main concept of the science of psychology. In the psychology of the 20th and 21st centuries, there were two views and approaches to explain the socio-psychological nature of this issue, and they differ sharply from each other.

According to the first approach, self-awareness is precisely the consciousness that has changed its direction. This interpretation is widespread in Russian psychology and is studied by L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontev, V.V. Stolin and their students. The essence of the second approach S.L. It is reflected in Rubinstein's scientific works. Self-awareness in the interpretation of the manifestations of the first approach: L.S. According to Vygotsky's personal opinion, self-awareness is manifested as a process that creates unity (generality) among different meanings and as an acquired consciousness. A.N. According to Leontev's interpretation, the conflict between essence and content in the individual consciousness explains the content essence of self-awareness.

I.S. Kohn reveals the concept of "I" as an active-creative, integrative premise that creates not only self-awareness for the individual, but also the possibility of conscious direction and control of his activities, that this concept has a dual nature. emphasizes. . Self-awareness includes a twofold "I": 1) "I" as a thinking subject, reflexive "I" - active, mobile, subject-dependent, existential "I" "; 2) "I" as an object of perception and inner intuition - the concept of "I" belonging to the object, "I-concept", a reflexive, unique phenomenon, the level of "I" or the image of "I".

The reflexive "I" consists of a cognitive drawing, with the help of which an individual constructs his social perception and ideas about others. The cognitive map includes two systems: personal and social similarity. PERSONALITY includes defining one's orientation in terms of physical, intellectual, and moral dimensions.

Social similarity consists of individual similarities and is determined by a person's belonging to different social groups: race, nationality, class, gender, etc. Along with personal similarity, social similarity is considered the main controller of self-awareness and social behavior.

Since the "I-concept" includes only those that are understood, it can be defined as a conscious cognitive perception and self-evaluation of an individual, i.e., expressing thoughts and judgments about himself. Most foreign authors U. According to views summarized by Hewitt, "Menconception" includes several components.

Self-esteem is an important driver of behavior as it relates to personality. A person's interactions with others, his criticality towards himself, demandingness, attitude to achievements and shortcomings depend on self-evaluation. What is the content of self-assessment? As one learns about another person's qualities, one gains the necessary information to develop a personal assessment. The evaluation formed about the PERSONAL "I" is the result of regular comparison with what the person sees in other people and his own observations. A person, knowing some things in himself, compares himself with him, assumes that the other person is not indifferent to his personal qualities, actions, expressions; all of these relate to the self-evaluation of a person and determine his mental mood. In other words, a person always has a referent group (real or idea), because a person assimilates his values in it, he counts with this group, his ideals and interests, etc., are also ideals and interests of the person.

V.V. Stolining to Stolin, the basis of self-awareness lies in the conflict between the content and the essence of the "I". The founder of the second direction S.L. On the basis of Rubinstein's research, we focus on researching the problem of self-awareness, and we consider it appropriate to pay attention to its subject, that is, the individual. In other words, the source of the formation of self-awareness is not

consciousness and its contradictions, but the formation and development of the individual in the social environment.

The life of people, the general living conditions are the objective conditions of mental activity in a special state (situation) - writes S.L. Rubinstein. The formation of a person's intended connection with his subjectivity in the process of self-realization and the resulting new qualitative state means that he is completely free from previous internal conflicts. Therefore, in this scientific approach, the functioning of self-awareness as a continuous mental process is determined by the conflict between a person's perceptions of other people and their relationship to him.

Normally, when a person thinks about himself, of course, he analyzes the results of his interactions with other people and creates his "I" based on their effectiveness. S. L. Rubinstein and K. A. Abulkhanova - Slavskaya emphasize that the inner essence of self-awareness is characterized by two foundations. The first of the basis is the content of human environment and interpersonal relations. His second is the expression of the possibility of thinking about these relations. The first of these has a social, i.e., objective nature, while the second is subjective, therefore, it depends on the psychophysiological and mental characteristics of a person. The compatibility or incompatibility of both bases with each other creates clear, true perceptions of identity, "I". According to the authors, sociality penetrates into the mind and psyche of a person, becomes a source of consciousness, self-awareness and control.

After all, when talking about the socialization of a person, this approach implies the socialization of his consciousness, and thus the place and role of self-awareness in socialization is explained in this way. According to this approach, there is a continuous interaction between psyche and socialization in the process of self-realization. The mutual content of relations is created. In our opinion, sociality is manifested in a person at the stage of subjectivity of self-awareness. Therefore, it is

unnatural to separate and explain the issues between spirituality and sociality as separate problems.

A person is a person not because of his self-awareness, but also because of the existence of an internal desire, drive, motive for self-awareness. Sociability thus expresses the necessary demand and desire for self-realization in a person. However, if this is the case, understanding of the nature and level of sociality, that is, humanity, from a psychological point of view, is the understanding of the nature of these needs, interests, aspirations, and thus the process of creating a personal goal in relation to one's life and activities. Based on the above considerations, we can give two different definitions of moral self-awareness:

A) Self is defined as self-awareness based on one or another ethical and moral norms and rules;

B) In our opinion, moral self-awareness is a desire to affirm oneself as a human being and thus to form humanity in one's self.

If a person does not recognize himself as a human being, it is impossible to develop human qualities. Self-awareness is the process or state of manifestation as an important tool for a person to realize this recognition.

Self-assessment is one of the components of self-awareness, which includes a person's assessment of his abilities, moral qualities and actions, and his knowledge about himself. Self-assessment can be adequate or inadequate. Adequate self-evaluation allows a person to have a critical attitude towards himself, to correctly assess his strength in accordance with the tasks of various difficulties and the demands of others. A person who has adequate self-esteem correctly evaluates his abilities and capabilities, does what he can do perfectly, saying "I can do it", and does what he can't do. "I'm sorry, I can't do it," he admits in time.

Moral self-awareness is a person's values, norms and ideals that are a reflection of his life-practical and historical experience. It works as a mechanism of social regulation, allowing a person to evaluate his own and other people's actions. Referring to certain moral standards, principles, ideals, good and bad, conscience and honor, justice, etc., it is possible to identify the phenomena of moral self-awareness and distinguish them from other forms of spiritual culture.

Moral self-awareness has three components:

1. The cognitive component is a set of moral principles, knowledge, ideas, concepts, judgments that a person perceives his moral qualities.
2. The emotional component reflects an emotional-valuable attitude to moral standards, an attitude towards oneself, moral self-esteem, emotional evaluation of interpersonal relationships.
3. Behavioral component - it determines the readiness for a certain course of action, as well as the level of personal responsibility for one's behavior.

Studies aimed at studying the moral consciousness of citizens of modern Russia, China, and the United States have shown that moral self-awareness is multifaceted, characterized by a complex structure, and certain categories of moral consciousness can be determined by various psychological and social factors. (culture, gender, age, etc.).

- In moral self-awareness, moral and value principles and the phenomenon of amoralism coexist and are psychologically compatible;
- The phenomenon of amoralism is the main feature in moral consciousness. Descriptors of immorality distinguish people more than moral values and principles;
- Ways to solve moral dilemmas are not directly related to moral values: different types of moral consciousness can arrive at the same solution based on completely different moral values and principles.

- Moral values, immorality, ways of resolving moral dilemmas, decency, goals in life are autonomous, they are different domains of moral self-awareness, each with its own dimensions.

In Russian psychology, the moral development of a child is understood as the process of his assimilation of moral social norms, standards, methods and forms of behavior (L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev, P. I. Galperin, L. I. Bozovich, etc.). through experience, awareness and conscious acceptance. Some authors distinguish social and individual forms of moral consciousness.

Social form is a historically formed and recognized system of ideas about what should be in society, reflects social life through the prism of "good and bad", embodies moral standards, principles, ideals of a particular society and regulates people's behavior. An individual form is a holistic personal formation that regulates a person's behavior on the basis of accepted and mastered moral standards based on the values of "good and bad". Individual moral consciousness is manifested in the ability to think morally and helps to choose actions freely and responsibly. In the study of a local psychologist, B. S. Bratus moral self-awareness is considered as a set of semantic personal formations. The general semantic formations of the personality directly determine the main and relatively constant attitude of a person to the main spheres of his life: to the whole world, to people, to himself. Personal values are defined as general meanings of life that are realized and accepted by a person. The entire set of semantic formations of a person forms a moral position and performs cognitive-rational, emotional-evaluative and regulatory functions, stimulates the moral activity of a person.

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